

GENDER DIFFERENCES IN SPATIAL THINKING ONLINE TRAINING

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Abstract

Spatial thinking concerns the ability to imagine objects and manipulate them mentally. It is not only essential for fulfilling everyday tasks, such as using a GPS, filling the fridge or organising furniture in a room, but it is also a predictor for successful performance in STEM areas (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics). This field is nowadays a cornerstone in our society, as it promotes economic growth and the creation of new jobs. Nonetheless, the representation of women in this domain is considerably smaller than that of men, which translates into less women accessing jobs with higher salaries and career opportunities. Among the different reasons for that, the focus of this work is on the gender gap in spatial thinking that favours males. Although the origins of these differences are yet not clear, several evidence confirms that despite there exist a genetic component, both females and males can improve their spatial skills through practice.

Gender differences in spatial tasks performance have been widely examined, focusing mainly on mental rotation and spatial orientation. However, there are no known studies that aim at examining these differences in various categories of spatial thinking. This work presents an analysis of gender differences for spatial ability and visual perception categories, based on the outcomes of the spatial thinking skills online training platform RIF 3.0 on users aged from 7 to 16 years old from Spain and Austria (N=20.352) in between November 2019 and June 2022. Activities meant for developing visualization, form constancy, position in space, transformation in space, object combination, spatial visualization, mental rotation, spatial relations, and spatial orientation skills are used. The results were statistically analysed and compared. Preliminary findings suggest that there are gender differences in some of the subcategories of spatial ability and visual perception studied, yet some of these differences favour girls over boys. This work intends to provide new insights into the matter of gender gap in spatial skills to generate well-grounded knowledge to adjust instruction to the needs of students.

Keywords: Spatial thinking, gender differences, STEM, spatial ability, visual perception, visualization.

1 INTRODUCTION

Spatial thinking is an umbrella term used to comprise different concepts, such as spatial perception, spatial ability, visual perception and spatial intelligence [1]. It refers to the ability to imagine, rotate, mirror and move objects, as well as being able to mentally take other perspectives [1]. Besides being necessary for fulfilling everyday tasks (e.g. navigating using a GPS, park our cars or filling our fridges), it is considered a strong predictor for success in STEM (i.e. Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) [2–4]. Additionally, having high spatial skills is linked to higher probability of choosing a STEM career [3].

The STEM field has proven to be essential to promote both individual growth, as people working on this area earn on average more than non-STEM workers, and societal development, since this industry boosts a more prosperous and innovative economy, as well as more productivity in research and development [5,6]. However, this sector is facing a significant gender gap. According to the PISA results of 2015 (Programme for International Student Assessment), there are two significant factors of interest [7]: First, on average, boys scored higher in mathematics and science, while girls did better in reading. Second, boys displayed more confidence and interest in learning science. Consequently, girls are less likely to choose a STEM career. In numbers, in 2020, the 6,8% of the Bachelor's students in science, math, computing, engineering, manufacturing and construction in Europe were women, compared to the 13.8% that made men [8]. This leads to an underrepresentation of women in STEM, which contributes to having less promising career perspectives [2] and to the gender salary gap [9].

Spatial thinking training might be a good solution to address this issue, as research shows that, though it is yet not clear if one is born with this ability or it mainly depends on nurture, it can be improved through practice [10, 11]. Nonetheless, spatial thinking is not absent of gender differences itself. Gender differences in spatial tasks performance have been widely studied, being the categories of mental-rotation and spatial orientation the ones that induce the largest cognitive dissimilarities between genders

[12, 13]. These usually appear from the age of puberty [14], although there are some studies that indicate that they can emerge at around 10 years [15]. The origin of these gender differences is however yet not clear. Some theories argue for psycho-social causes, based on the influence of experiences, attitudes and stereotypes, while others support a biological perspective, pointing out the significance of brain organization and hormonal influences [14]. Whatever the causes, there is several evidence that verifies that spatial thinking can be improved through practice by either females and males [16].

With this very same purpose of training spatial thinking skills, the online platform RIF 2.0 was launched by a group of experts from the University of Salzburg and other universities and universities of education in Austria in 2019 [17]. It offers more than 700 interactive tasks for participants aged 13 and over, and in the framework of less than two years, it counted with the participation of more than 45.000 users [date of the data: 2.6.2022]. Given its success, the version 3.0 of the platform is being developed (see <https://adi3d.at/rif30/>), where now the additional target is primary school children between 7 and 12 years, and for whom several tasks for training and diagnosis are offered. The activities are framed in the categories of visual perception (i.e. visualization, form constancy, position in space, transformation in space and object combination) and spatial ability (i.e. spatial visualization, mental rotation, spatial orientation and spatial relations).

Reviewing the literature available, it becomes clear that there are numerous investigations on gender differences in spatial thinking training, focusing mostly on mental rotation. However, there are no known studies that aim at observing these differences in all the subcategories of the categories of visual perception and spatial ability across several ages. Learning about this would provide further information about the development of spatial thinking in children, which can have a great impact in mathematics and science education [18]. Moreover, it would in the knowledge about the RIF 3.0 platform, its improvement and application as a learning tool.

Considering this, the general objective of this work is to study in what subcategories of spatial thinking do gender differences appear and how does age interact with these. More specifically, the research questions that guide this study are:

- 1 Are there gender differences in one or more of the nine subcategories of spatial thinking trained in the RIF 3.0 platform?
- 2 Does age influence in the gender differences?

2 METHODOLOGY

For the analysis of the nine subcategories of visual perception and spatial ability, 43 tests were used, which were formed by 30 to 60 tasks each. More specifically, the distribution of the tests was as follows: *visualization* = 6; *form constancy* = 3; *position in space* = 2; *transformation in space* = 5; *object combination* = 3; *mental rotation* = 6; *spatial relations* = 6; *spatial orientation* = 6; and *spatial visualization* = 6.

A group of primary and secondary school students ($N = 20.352$; 9.332 girls, 11.020 boys; age range: 7-16 years) from Austria and Spain participated in this study. From these, 3235 solved the activities for the first category (i.e. visual perception) and 17117 solved the tasks for the second category (i.e. spatial ability). The age range from 7 to 16 years old has been divided into five age groups: 1 (7 to 8); 2 (9 to 10); 3 (11 to 12); 4 (13 to 14); and 5 (15 to 16).

The results for the category of spatial ability were collected from November 2019, until June 2022. The link to the website was sent to different schools from Austria and participants took part voluntarily and anonymously.

To obtain the data of the category of visual perception, two methods were used. For the Spanish students ($n = 94$), four classes of the fifth and sixth grade in two schools in Chiclana de la Frontera, Cádiz, were visited. As for the Austrian participants ($n = 3.141$), the webpage link was sent to different schools, and data was received from those who chose to take part voluntarily.

Results were analysed using SPSS. As the results were not normally distributed and, in many cases, the sample size was smaller than 120, the Mann & Whitney U-test was used to compare results between females and males.

Outcomes of participants who chose the box “else” for the gender option were not considered, they did not serve for the purpose of this work.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Visual perception

For all the subcategories of visual perception, girls systematically outperform boys, being the difference in some of them statistically significant. The detailed results for each subcategory are described below.

3.1.1 Visualization

In the subcategory of visualization girls performed significantly better than boys overall ($p = .000$). This scenario is repeated along the age range from 7 to 14, however, differences are not significant for children between 7 and 8 years old. Boys of the age group from 15 to 16 years old slightly outperformed girls.

Table 1. Results for the subcategory visualization by gender and age group.

	Overall			7-8			9-10			11-12			13-14			15-16		
	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n
Females	90,37	10,46	1029	84,31	11,48	13	88,64	9,76	88	88,97	12,42	361	91,99	8,69	529	87,02	10,41	38
Males	86,09	12,23	798	78,80	17,69	10	84,94	11,83	86	84,80	13,43	306	87,31	10,91	357	89,60	11,45	38
p	.000**			.430			.032*			.000**			.000**			.065		

3.1.2 Form constancy

The results of the activities related with form constancy show that, in general, females outscored males significantly ($p = .000$). When considering every age group, girls of the first, third and fourth age groups performed better than boys, only being significant for the third ($p = .000$) and fourth ($p = .002$). Additionally, the sample size in the age group from 7 to 8 is not to be compared due to the difference in number of participants. On the contrary, boys of the second and fifth age group performed better, but not statistically significant ($p = .746$; $p = .445$).

Table 2. Results for the subcategory form constancy by gender and age group.

	Overall			7-8			9-10			11-12			13-14			15-16		
	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n
Females	90,57	11,27	279	89,83	2,59	2	82,58	15,08	22	90,36	12,95	82	92,46	8,23	132	82,81	15,41	7
Males	86,19	14,77	281	88,26	11,02	10	83,63	19,38	35	83,10	17,88	82	89,11	9,08	110	90,25	13,38	8
p	.000**			.746			.515			.000**			.002**			.445		

3.1.3 Position in space

In the subcategory of position in space, girls got better results than boys in overall, however not significant ($p = .064$). More specifically, on the one hand, females outperformed males from the ages of 11 to 14, being this difference significant for the ages 13 to 14 ($p = .002$). These two age groups count with a larger sample than the other three groups. On the other hand, males do better than females from 7 to 10 and 15 to 16 years old, being significant from 9 to 10. Nonetheless, the sample in these cases are considerably smaller.

Table 3. Results for the subcategory position in space by gender and age group.

	Overall			7-8			9-10			11-12			13-14			15-16		
	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n
Females	82,77	17,72	159	71,53	11,13	13	65,91	24,48	13	85,08	11,80	51	87,20	12,82	78	78,18	16,56	4
Males	80,72	14,73	196	81,90	7,64	6	85,04	8,98	12	80,52	13,63	76	81,75	13,80	96	82,83	22,74	6
p	.064			.064			.009**			.059			.002**			.449		

3.1.4 Transformation in space

For the activities targeted at training the subcategory of transformation in space, on the whole, females outscored males, though not significantly ($p = .306$). From the ages 11 to 14, the same pattern is found. Nonetheless, it should be noted that there is a substantial difference between the female sample size

(n= 120) in the age group of 11 to 12, and that of males (n= 36). For the other age groups, boys perform better than girls, however, comparisons are again not very representative, as the sample sizes are not equal. This is especially important for the ages between 7 and 8, as there is no female participants.

Table 4. Results for the subcategory transformation in space by gender and age group.

	Overall			7-8			9-10			11-12			13-14			15-16		
	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n
Females	76,47	16,86	229	-	-	0	79,60	14,85	23	76,41	16,27	120	78,10	13,28	77	55,28	36,33	9
Males	73,47	19,48	129	69,88	13,04	4	84,00	4,00	3	75,14	15,52	36	72,88	19,80	67	71,45	27,03	19
p	.306			-			.597			.606			.273			.324		

3.1.5 Object combination

Concerning the results for object combination, females performed significantly better than males in overall (p= .015). Boys only scored higher than girls in the first age group, however not significant (p= .333). Moreover, the sample size for this age group was particularly small; therefore, results are not representative. In addition, in the case of the second age group there was only one female participant, therefore comparisons are not coherent.

Table 5. Results for the subcategory object combination by gender and age group.

	Overall			7-8			9-10			11-12			13-14			15-16		
	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n
Females	86,27	14,62	59	54,00	14,14	2	4,00	-	1	89,16	9,12	13	89,22	5,50	37	80,26	21,00	6
Males	83,96	11,48	76	73,67	13,67	2	75,67	10,84	2	83,69	9,54	15	85,09	9,10	52	75,64	28,39	5
p	.015*			.333			-			.077			.036			1,000		

3.1.6 Correlation between age and results

Results show a very weak positive correlation for all the categories, except for transformation in space, in which the correlation is negative.

Table 6. Correlation between age and results.

	<i>Spearman</i>	<i>p</i>
Visualization	,131**	.000
Form constancy	,160**	.000
Position in space	,189**	.000
Transformation in space	-,048	.367
Object combination	,139	.108

** significant at the 0,01 level

3.2 Spatial ability

For all the subcategories of spatial ability, boys significantly outperform girls. The specific results for each subcategory are presented below.

3.2.1 Spatial visualization

In the subcategory of spatial visualization, males perform better than girls both in general (p= .000), but also in every age group. However, this difference is only significant for the ages of 15 to 16 (p= .000). For the ages of 9 to 12, no comparisons are possible as the sample sizes are too small and there is only one male participant.

Table 7. Results for the subcategory spatial visualization by gender and age group.

	Overall			7-8			9-10			11-12			13-14			15-16		
	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n
Females	64,51	18,41	2486	70,28	26,97	6	38,33	11,78	2	37,22	48,10	3	61,45	17,62	451	65,24	18,46	2024
Males	66,62	16,27	3071	76,33	17,73	5	70,00	-	1	96,67	-	1	62,68	18,51	476	67,32	19,32	2588
p	.000**			.854			-			-			.261			.000**		

3.2.2 Mental rotation

Regarding mental rotation, boys significantly ($p = .000$) outperform girls in all the categories where analysis were viable, as from the ages of 7 to 12 there were almost none or no participants.

Table 8. Results for the subcategory mental rotation by gender and age group.

	Overall			7-8			9-10			11-12			13-14			15-16		
	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n
Females	53,35	20,845	1509	-	-	0	95,00	-	1	40,00	-	1	50,86	20,53	259	53,84	20,86	1248
Males	60,01	21,44	1948	20,00	-	1	-	-	0	25,00	-	1	57,20	18,88	271	60,51	21,77	1675
p	.000**			-			-			-			.000**			.000**		

3.2.3 Spatial relations

In the case of the subcategory spatial relations, males significantly outscore females in overall ($p = .000$) and in the age group of 15 to 16 ($p = .000$). For the ages of 13 to 14, girls perform minimally better than boys, but not significantly ($p = .673$). As in the previous subcategory, analysis for the ages of 7 to 13 were not possible, as there were no results for some of them.

Table 9. Results for the subcategory spatial relations by gender and age group.

	Overall			7-8			9-10			11-12			13-14			15-16		
	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n
Females	51,34	16,43	1740	-	-	0	44,89	333,32	4	40,91	16,07	2	48,90	15,90	208	51,70	16,43	1526
Males	54,06	17,03	2310	50,65	28,92	7	-	-	0	-	-	0	48,67	15,68	227	54,66	17,03	2076
p	.000**			-			-			-			.673			.000**		

3.2.4 Spatial orientation

For the tasks aimed at spatial orientation, boys significantly outperform girls in overall ($p = .000$), and in the age groups of 13 to 14 ($p = .005$) and 15 to 16 ($p = .000$). From 11 to 12 the differences are not representative as the sample size is small. From 7 to 10 no comparisons are possible due to the sample size.

Table 10. Results for the subcategory spatial orientation by gender and age group.

	Overall			7-8			9-10			11-12			13-14			15-16		
	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n	X (%)	Std.	n
Females	74,14	16,91	1842	75,00	-	1	66,67	11,55	3	18,75	20,97	4	71,73	16,66	350	74,88	16,69	1484
Males	77,50	16,51	2211	69,17	27,82	6	30,00	-	1	20,00	13,23	3	74,94	16,48	309	78,06	16,25	1892
p	.000**			-			-			.463			.005**			.000**		

3.2.5 Correlation between age and results

Results show a very weak positive correlation for all the categories, except for transformation in space, in which the correlation is negative.

Table 11. Correlation between age and results.

	<i>Spearman</i>	<i>p</i>
Spatial visualization	,090**	.000
Mental rotation	,066**	.000
Spatial relations	,089**	.000
Spatial orientation	,099**	.000

* significant at the 0,01 level

4 CONCLUSIONS

The conclusions drawn from the analysis of the results received for the tasks aimed at training the spatial thinking categories of visual perception and spatial ability are described below.

First, for the category of visual perception, it is observed that girls outperform boys systematically. Although there are some specific cases for some age groups in which the outcomes are reversed (boys perform better than girls), they occur at a lower rate. Nevertheless, in all the subcategories except for object combination, males in the ages of 15 to 16 outscore girls, though not significantly. These results are in line with previous research that state puberty as the age when differences in spatial ability appear [14,19]. In any case, it is worth mentioning that the sample size for this age group is not large, therefore these results may not be representative enough. As for the category of spatial ability, boys are significantly better than girls in all the subcategories. In this occasion, although the sample size is larger in general, there is only representative data for the ages from 13 to 16, therefore, results of earlier ages are not conclusive.

These outcomes provide new insights for the gender differences topic in spatial thinking. There are no known studies in which results show that girls perform better than boys in any type of activity. This opens new doors for research, as there are several variables that may be influencing these effects: the time spent solving the tasks; the fact that they were designed by young women as opposed to the tasks of the spatial ability category, that were designed by men; or their difficulty (as this situation appears for the category of visual perception, which is aimed at children from 7 to 12 years old. In any case, it is noteworthy how gender differences are inverted in the category of visual perception and spatial ability, shedding light on the fact that spatial thinking is not a linear skill, but formed by several sufficiently differentiated areas.

Furthermore, further investigation on these activities should be focused on how to decrease the gender gap in the second category of activities (i.e. spatial ability), as it is where the largest differences are found. For this purpose, conducting longer interventions in which students have the opportunity to practice several times and providing feedback to reinforce the correct answers and revise the incorrect ones might be an effective approach.

Second, there is no evidence that age is a cause of these gender differences, as there are no strong correlations between age and the results obtained. However, the significant differences of the sample sizes between age groups does not allow to draw unequivocal conclusions. Therefore, future research should aimed at analysing results from a larger and more balanced sample, so that not only the correlation between age and results can be studied, but also if gender differences change through age.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Maresch G, Sorby SA. Perspectives on Spatial Thinking. *J Geom. Graph.* 2021;25(2):271-93.
- [2] Ruthsatz' V, Neuburger' S, Quaiser-Pohl' C. The social relevance and the socio-cultural origins of gender differences in spatial abilities. *Folia Sociologica.* 2012;43:17-32.

- [3] Wai J, Lubinski D, Benbow CP. Spatial ability for STEM domains: Aligning over 50 years of cumulative psychological knowledge solidifies its importance. *J Educ Psychol*. 2009 Nov;101(4):817–35.
- [4] Buckley J, Seery N, Canty D. A Heuristic Framework of Spatial Ability: a Review and Synthesis of Spatial Factor Literature to Support its Translation into STEM Education. *Educ Psychol Rev*. 2018 Sep;30(3):947–72.
- [5] Ismail Z. Benefits of STEM Education. 2018;14.
- [6] Bacovic M, Andrijasevic Z, Pejovic B. STEM Education and Growth in Europe. *J Knowl Econ* [Internet]. 2021 Jul 4 [cited 2022 Apr 13]; Available from: <https://link.springer.com/10.1007/s13132-021-00817-7>
- [7] Stoet G, Geary DC. The Gender-Equality Paradox in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics Education. *Psychol Sci*. 2018 Apr;29(4):581–93.
- [8] Eurostat. Graduates in tertiary education, in science, math., computing, engineering, manufacturing, construction, by sex - per 1000 of population aged 20-29. [Internet]. [Cited 2022 July 18]. Available from: https://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=educ_uoe_grad04&lang=en.
- [9] Kahn S, Ginther D. Women and STEM. National Bureau of Economic Research; 2017.
- [10] Taylor HA, Hutton A. Think3d!: Training Spatial Thinking Fundamental to STEM Education. *Cogn Instr*. 2013 Oct;31(4):434–55.
- [11] Montello DR, Grossner K, Janelle DG. 1 Concepts for Spatial Learning and Education: An Introduction. *R*. 2014;28.
- [12] Moon Y, Jo H, Kim J, Ryu J. Exploring Gender Differences in Spatial Orientation Ability on Representing Cognitive Map. *Int J Psychol Behav Sci*. 2016;8.
- [13] Neuburger S, Ruthsatz V, Jansen P, Quaiser-Pohl C. Can girls think spatially? Influence of implicit gender stereotype activation and rotational axis on fourth graders' mental-rotation performance. *Learn Individ Differ*. 2015 Jan;37:169–75.
- [14] Quaiser-Pohl C, Jansen P, Lehmann J, Kudielka BM. Is there a relationship between the performance in a chronometric mental-rotations test and salivary testosterone and estradiol levels in children aged 9-14 years?: Mental Rotation and Salivary Hormones in (Pre-)Puberty. *Dev Psychobiol*. 2016 Jan;58(1):120–8.
- [15] Neuburger S, Jansen P, Heil M, Quaiser-Pohl C. A Threat in the Classroom: Gender Stereotype Activation and Mental-Rotation Performance in Elementary-School Children. *Z Für Psychol*. 2012 Jan;220(2):61–9.
- [16] Uttal DH, Meadow NG, Tipton E, Hand LL, Alden AR, Warren C, et al. The malleability of spatial skills: A meta-analysis of training studies. *Psychol Bull*. 2013 Mar;139(2):352–402.
- [17] Maresch G, Müller-Kreutzer J. NEU in RIF 2.0: Nach Alter, Geschlecht und Aufgabenset. 2021;3.
- [18] Linn MC, Petersen A. C. Emergence and Characterization of Sex Differences in Spatial Ability: A Meta-Analysis. 1985;21.
- [19] Neuburger S, Jansen P, Heil M, Quaiser-Pohl C. Gender differences in pre-adolescents' mental-rotation performance: Do they depend on grade and stimulus type? *Personal Individ Differ*. 2011 Jun;50(8):1238–42.